

A Study on the Complex Formation by Amino and Amido Derivatives of Thiophene

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Manuscript received 18 November 1974; revised 24 March 1975; accepted 10 April 1975

Formation constants of complexes formed by (I) 2-thenylamine (2-TA), (II) tetrahydro-2-thenylamine (THTA), (III) 5-methyl tetrahydro-2-thenylamine (5-MeTHTA) (IV) benzylamine (BZA), (V) thiophene-2-carboxamide (TCAMD) with metal ions like Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II) and Ag(I), are measured at $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$ at 0.1M NaClO₄ ionic strength. Metal-sulphur interaction is suggested for Ag(I) complex with 2-TA. Irving and Williams' order is not followed by Co(II) with 2-TA and TCAMD. With the amine ligands for Zn(II) and Ag(I) the order of successive stabilities is $\log K_2 > \log K_1$.

LIGAND properties of thiophene derivatives have been attracting attention of workers since the last decade. The carboxylates¹⁻⁴ and Schiff bases⁵ have been investigated. But little work have been done on amino and amido derivatives. 2-thenyl amine was studied by Gonick *et al.*⁶ with Ag(I), Hg(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) etc. for complex formation in aqueous solution but all metal ions except Ag(I) were precipitated as hydroxides and formation constant for Ag(I) could only be measured. These authors could find no interaction of the metals with sulphur. We could however, prepare a number of complexes with this ligand and various metal ions in dry ethanolic medium, and have been able to measure the formation constants in 50% V/V aq.dioxane.

Gould *et al.*⁷ have recently investigated acetamide complexes of Hg(II). Gillespie⁸ *et al.* have proved by N.M.R. studies that the carbonyl group is protonated by the rearrangement,

And this proton is displaced in complex formation.

We report here the complex formation by (i) 2-thenyl amine (2-TA), (ii) tetrahydro-2-thenyl amine (THTA), (iii) 5-methyl tetrahydro-2-thenyl amine, (5MeTHTA), (iv) Benzyl amine (BZA), and (v) Thiophene-2-carboxamide (TCAMD) with metal ions like Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Co(II), Hg(II) and Ag(I) in 50% V/V aqueous dioxane medium. All the possible metal ion ligand pairs, however, could not be studied. Apart from the measurement of

formation constants the purpose was to study the coordinating tendency of both the N and S atoms in the ligand molecules with metal ions. The tetrahydro derivatives were used to activate sulphur for coordination by removing the aromaticity of the ring. The metal ions include soft and mixed hard-soft acids. With soft acids M-S π interaction is expected. BZA is included for comparison. The measurements are done by Bjerrum, Calvin pH titration technique⁹ as modified by Irving and Rossotti¹⁰.

Experimental

All chemicals were of A.R. and G.R. grade. Thiophene-2-aldehyde and 5-methylthiophene-2-aldehyde were received from K and K laboratories, Inc., U.S.A.

Preparation of the Ligands :

2-Thenyl amine was prepared by a process of amino methylation with thiophene, formaldehyde and ammonium chloride as described by Hartough¹¹. The final product was obtained by distilling twice under reduced pressure (Found : b.p. $82^{\circ}/17$ mm; η_D^{26} 1.5541, m.p. of hydrochloride $188^{\circ}-190^{\circ}$, reported : b.p. $82^{\circ}/17$ mm; η_D^{20} 1.5615, m.p. of hydrochloride 192° ; Found : C, 40.28; H, 5.25; N, 9.25%. Calculated for C₅H₇NSHCl : C, 40.16; H, 5.36; N, 9.37%).

Tetrahydro-2-thenyl amine was prepared by two methods. (1) Reduction of thiophene-2-aldehyde-oxime by 2.5% Na/Hg as described by Putokhin and Egorova¹². (2) By hydrogenation of 2-thenyl amine with Pd/C catalyst¹³. 845 mg of 2-TA was reduced under 45 lbs/sq.inch pressure of hydrogen in presence of 5 g of the catalyst. The fall of pressure, as calculated for 4 atoms of hydrogen was obtained within half an hour. The yields in both cases were,

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however, very poor (about a few tens of mgs.), after going through the processes of purification (Reported : n_D^{15} 1.5399, Found : n_D^{31} 1.531, m.p. of hydrochloride 142° - 143° . Reported : b.p. $69.5^\circ/10$ mm; Found : $71^\circ/10$ mm; Found : C, 39.20; H, 7.51; N, 9.10%. Calc. for $C_5H_{11}NSHCl$: C, 39.12; H, 7.82; N, 9.12%).

5-MeTHTA was prepared by reduction of 5-methylthiophene-2-aldoxime by 2.5% Na/Hg after the method of Putokhin and Egorova¹², b.p. $62^\circ/10$ mm. n_D^{24} 1.543, m.p. of the hydrochloride salt is 186° - 188° . [Analysis Found : C, 42.81; H, 8.45; N, 8.25%. Calc. for $C_6H_{13}NSHCl$: C, 43.01; H, 8.36; N, 8.28%] Thiophene-2-carboxamide¹² was prepared from thiophene-2-carboxylic acid (m.p. 173° ; reported : 173°).

Preparation of metal perchlorates are reported^{1,2}. In general all the titrations were carried out in a 100 ml beaker in a water thermostat maintained at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. The pH measurements were done with a Cambridge valve bench type pH meter. All the measuring apparatus were certified and of A type. Solution for metal titration was 20 ml of 50% V/V dioxane-water containing 0.001M metal ion, 0.005M ligand hydrochloride, 0.1M $NaClO_4$ and 0.0025M $HClO_4$. Solution for ligand titration was the same as above, but without the metal. Solution for mineral acid titration was the same as above except the metal and ligand. The titrant was 0.1M carbonate free NaOH solution.

In case of Ag(I) and Hg(II) pure aqueous amines were used as titrant as was described by Irving and Rossotti (second method)¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

The stability constant are calculated by assuming maximum coordination of 2. $\frac{\bar{n}}{(\bar{n}-1)[L]}$ is plotted against $\frac{(2-\bar{n})[L]}{(\bar{n}-1)}$ in large graph papers (not shown here) and points which fall on a straight line are chosen for calculation, of K_1 and K_2 by the method of least

squares¹⁴. $\log {}^pK_1^H$ values for the protonated ligands are calculated by usual methods. All the values of ${}^pK_1^H$ and $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ are shown in the table. The gaps in the table indicate that the values could not be obtained due to precipitation. From the scatter of points about the straight line plot the calculated error in the stability constants is $\pm 0.01 \log K$.

The formation constants of the complexes of metal ions and the sulphur containing ligands show absence of considerable metal-sulphur interaction in most cases. The ${}^pK_1^H$ values of the ligands are of the order $TCAMD > BZA > 5-MeTHTA > 2-TA > THTA$. $\log K_1$ values of Cu(II) follow this order for all these ligands. With 2-TA, Cu forms the strongest complex. The formation constants for 1:1 complex show that Irving and Williams' order¹⁵ is not followed by Co(II). Low value for Cd(II) shows absence of metal sulphur interaction. The $\log K_1$ values for Ag(I), Ni(II) and Co(II) for BZA and 2-TA has the order $2-TA > BZA$. This suggests extra interaction in these cases. For Ag(I) complexes with 2-TA and BZA in aqueous medium, Gonick *et al.*⁶ found the order $BZA > 2-TA$ [${}^pK_1^H$: BZA, 9.48; 2-TA, 8.97; $\log K_1$: BZA, 3.02; 2-TA, 2.87]. Though the increase of $\log K_1$ from BZA to 2-TA in present case is small, it is nevertheless, significant. This indicates possible solvent effect in promoting M-S π interaction, because sulphur in a less polar solvent would tend to be softer¹⁶.

For Zn(II) and Ag(I), $\log K_2 > \log K_1$ with 2-TA. This reversal of order with amine ligands is due to strong tendency of Ag(I) to form linear bonds with similar ligands¹⁷ (Gonick *et al.*⁶ also found $\log K_2 > \log K_1$). For Zn(II) such cases are known with amine ligands due to its tendency to form stronger Zn-amine tetrahedral species from a weak hexa-aquo octahedral structure¹⁷.

The synthesis of pure THTA was tedious and the yield was very poor so we were unable to carry out the experiments for all the metals. No extra interaction in metal-ligand complexes could, however, be

TABLE—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL-LIGAND COMPLEXES IN 50% V/V DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURE AT $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ WITH 0.1M $NaClO_4$ BACKGROUND

Ligand	$\log {}^pK_1^H$	Cu(II)		Ni(II)		Co(II)		Zn(II)		Cd(II)		Ag(I)		Hg(II)	
		$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$												
I 2-TA	8.25	4.97	4.02	3.25	—	3.93	3.53	3.05	4.22	2.56	—	2.14	2.69	—	—
II THTA	8.00	4.57	—	—	—	—	—	3.00	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
III 5-MeTHTA	8.42	4.86	4.53	3.18	2.62	2.99	—	3.50	3.89	2.47	—	—	—	—	—
IV BZA	8.58	5.20	3.88	3.12	—	2.68	—	3.34	4.13	2.72	—	2.05	2.57	5.98	—
V TCAMD	10.54	7.55	6.32	4.90	—	5.56	4.79	6.10	5.68	4.53	—	2.76	—	9.05	7.28

observed with this ligand. The value of PK_1^H and $\log K_1$ for Cu(II) and Zn(II) has decreased from those of 2-TA. This ligand did not interact with Co(II). The ligand 5-MeTHTA may be compared with 2-TA and BZA. The $\log K_1$ value of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Cd(II) are in the order 2-TA > 5-MeTHTA and for Zn(II) the order is 5-MeTHTA > 2-TA. This same order is however observed for $\log \beta_2$ values of Cu(II). Irving and Williams' order¹⁵ is followed and Cd(II) shows low value. For metal ions Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) the order of stabilities is 5-MeTHTA > BZA. For Zn(II) we may infer some M-S π interaction but for Ni(II) and Co(II) the reason may be in L.F.S.E. Unlike the tetrahydroderivative of thiophene carboxylic acid¹⁻² sulphur in 5-MeTHTA does not show any general increase in activity, which was expected, because of the removal of the aromaticity of the ring and the introduction of the electron repelling methyl group in the 5-position. For Zn(II) once again $\log K_2 > \log K_1$ ¹⁷ and the $\log K_1$ values of Ni and Zn has the order Zn > Ni.

Thiophene-2-carboxamide has a high PK_1^H value. The curve for ligand titration separates from mineral acid curve at a high B value. But curves for metal titration separates from the ligand curve at B values much lower than that for hydrolyses of the metals in 50% V/V aqueous dioxane. Calculation of \bar{n}_A are done by the formula

$$\bar{n}_A = \frac{PK_1^H \cdot \frac{1}{\text{antilog } B}}{1 + PK_1^H \cdot \frac{1}{\text{antilog } B}}$$

The $\log K_1$ values are also high. Irving and Williams' order is not followed by Co(II). The $\log K_1$ values for Zn and Ni are of the order Zn > Ni. The stability of Hg(II) complexes are the highest and Hg forms 1:2 complex. Ag(I) forms a weak complex.

Co(II) has not followed Irving and Williams' order with ligands 2-TA and TCAMD. And $\log K_1$ values of Co(II) and Ni(II) are in order Co > Ni. This order is observed by a number of workers¹⁸⁻²¹. Some attribute this to Jahn Teller stabilisation of Co(II) similar to Cu(II) and to favourable entropy effect.

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